

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF SELF-EDUCATION IN THE WORK OF ABU ABDULLAH MUHAMMAD IBN ALI HAKIM TERMEZI "THE WISE AND THE DECEIVED"

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Abstract: When the nafs brings falsehood, oppression, and lies, it blinds its owner, adorns him, deceives him, distracts him, and this deception continues. Airy desires are the chess of the nafs. He occupies the cells of truth one by one, and finally frees the soul from the truth. He who is deceived is deceived by his own inexperience and ignorance. He obeys the commands of the nafs with his heart. Hawaiian desires in the shadow of lust will gradually pass their judgment on lust.

Keywords: lust, lie, deception, heart, desire, ignorance, lust, truth, justice, correctness

INTRODUCTION

Praise be to Allah, the One who is worthy of praise. Messenger, prophet and blessings be upon his servant. We have seen that the religion of Allah has three pillars: truth, justice, built on righteousness. Righteousness is entrusted to the members, justice to the hearts, and righteousness to the minds. Tomorrow, when we approach the scale to weigh the deeds, the good deeds will be right, evils are placed on the circle of justice, on the tongue of the scales of righteousness. With that Good things like the end of God's pleasure from his servants to his servants the severity of the evils will be known. Anyone who is a combination of these three things: if if the truth disappears from it, falsehood will replace it. If justice is lost from him, instead oppression will come. If truth is lost from it, falsehood will replace it. These are the three things is the army of enlightenment. The three things that are against them are the air of lust is an army. Nafs is a container of air. He surrounds the deceived. Their desires are theirs In his affairs, he deceives with his desires, the air that falls into falsehood, oppression and lies.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Those who are deceived live their lives with the ears of the heart, their desires and desires one of the three things he commands is to listen and follow him. Lust is in the works if he brings falsehood, oppression, and lies, he blinds the owner, and shows him that deceives, misleads, and this deception continues.

This test is for siddiqs, ascetics, obeds, It is the same for the hypocrites and the zahir scholars, their minority is from this delusion stay healthy.[:3] If these people, who are religious leaders in appearance, are not saved from the deception of the self so how about "properties"? They were deceived by what their lusts adorned. Their actions are the hardships they endured in the path of righteousness, asceticism, prayer, and piety. looked great in their hearts. The beauty and beauty of these things, in particular, arose from these things pride made them proud. These beauties covered their inner evils. That's it for them things did not appear. That's why they spent their lives deceived. They are Allah Almighty they came to him with their bad deeds clearly shown to them. They do this knowing that it was good, their paths were blocked. "What Allah gave them that they did not take into account was seen", "The evil of their actions was seen", "He mocked them surrounded by things." Everyone will receive the destiny that Allah has decreed. Rasulullah (s.a.w.) said, "The one who apologizes to him while continuing to sin It is like laughing from the Lord" in this sense. Appearance of sins - There are open and hidden types. Allah Almighty says in His book "Sins Abandon what is open and what is hidden" (Surah An'am, verse 12). It is clear from the believers there are those who have left sin and have not left their hiding places. More sins from them abandoning the open and hidden in practice, but in thought, hesitation, and desire there are those who did not leave. This does not mean that he is still free from sin. A believer knows God and finds peace with faith. In the name of Islam is entitled and is called a Muslim, after which the nafs is led by airy desires comes with lusts. By the will of Allah, the soul will take its owner little by little when he takes over and deceives, he will divert him from his residence, from his goal takes away.[:4].

RESEARCH RESULTS

My father is from Salih ibn Muhammad, he is from Umar ibn Harun, he is Qudoma ibn Musa ibn From Qudoma, he from Ibn Maz'un, he from Rasulullah (s.a.v). He said: "To my Ummah from the errors of the scholars, the disobedience of the judges and the bad interpretation I'm afraid." Abu Abdullah (may Allah have mercy on him) said: "All of them are deceived. The knowing soul steps into ignorance only after it is blinded on the path of knowledge he will go astray." My father (may Allah have mercy on him) Abdullah ibn Maslama is from Magtabi, he is Kasir ibn Abdullah Ibn Awf narrates from Muzani, he narrates from his father, he from his grandfather, and he narrates from the Messenger of Allah (pbuh). U said: "What I fear most for my Ummah after myself is the error of a scholar, the rulership of the tyrant and the air to be followed is lust". It means ours equal to the first in our case. A wrong judge is a wrong judge. Follower Air desire is a

bad sign. The meaning of the two hadiths is the same, but the wording is different. Of those all are lost. Only after the knowing ego does not show him the path of knowledge is mistaken. He steps into ignorance and loses his way. A wise man is blinded by lust only then will he be inclined to lust and the world. The expositor makes a bad interpretation on his own weaves measurements and suspicions. The devil's measurements and suspicions are similar. He said, "I am better than him. You created me from fire." [:5-6]

DISCUSSION

What is the error of the scholars, the fatigue of the judges and the bad interpretation? "The error of the scholars is like a mirage that distracts the minds of Allah Almighty created and said to him: "Come." He came. Then he said to him: "Go." He's gone. Then Allah said: "By my power, I have not created anything dearer to me than you." You are the reason I take and I give because of you. I will rebuke you. The reward and the punishment are yours will be given," he said. Abu Abdullah (may Allah have mercy on him) said: "Allah blessed the monotheists with intelligence." made, gave people intelligence. They separate things because of that intelligence separate Muwahhids distinguish the good from the bad by reason. That's why God has forbidden khamr in his book. Then he is forbidden to his servants explaining the reason for doing it: "...it is the dirt that is the work of the devil, from it stay away! Perhaps then you will be saved" (Surat Al-Maida, verse 90). And you are believing brothers. It is the remembrance of Allah and He said that he would stop praying. Because it distracts the mind. And when the mind is gone, ugly things will come Accordingly, to return from the haram, the harm of the khamr, his said that it was dirty. And he said: "So stay away from the impurity of idols." Because xamr is also among idols. This is a huge mistake. That is why Rasulullah It is appropriate for the ummah of the Prophet (s.a.w.) to fear that they will go astray. That's it so is the case of the misguided in making the forbidden thing lawful. Messenger of Allah (s.a.v) said: "Allah makes lawful what he has forbidden, and he who makes it lawful for himself "he also cursed" is mutawatir.

CONCLUSION

The believers were freed from this attachment by the blessing of monotheism that God gave them. They worshiped only Allah. They believed that all benefits and harms are from Him alone. They only hoped for him. They prayed to him alone. Then there are pros and cons they were deceived by reasons. This is the work of the ego. And the heart, in every work, is a sign to God does. Considers it. Nafs, things, the reasons hidden in them reflects. His secret - "He gave it to you from the hands of men, from heaven, from the earth,

the sun, the moon, heat, cold, and behavior. He is the original giver. The wounded blocked Him from you. You will receive from them in front of your eyes. This is in his heart he demanded that you get these things from Allah Almighty.

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